

Welcome to the DATAMITE Newsletter

Our motto: Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data.

DATAMITE from a business point of view

Designed with real market needs in mind, **DATAMITE enables companies to unlock the value of their data**. It provides tailored monetisation strategies, open-source tools and actionable business models to achieve this. In the '**DATAMITE from a business point of view**' video series, we explore how DATAMITE facilitates fair data valuation, generates new business opportunities and establishes a foundation for the sustainable exploitation of data across European industries. To this end, we **interviewed four partners** responsible for some of DATAMITE's use cases.

Konstantinos Kontodimas and Iason Panagos from [HEDNO](#), a key partner in the development of DATAMITE pilots. From a business perspective, HEDNO demonstrates how the DATAMITE Framework empowers organisations to accelerate their digital transformation and enhances the efficiency and sustainability of electricity distribution networks.

Ricardo Henriques and Pedro Boto from [E-REDES](#), DATAMITE's partner leading the 'Leveraging Electricity Distribution Open Data' Pilot. From a business perspective, a refined version of the DATAMITE framework could be deployed and managed by E-REDES's DATAHUB to share data with external stakeholders. In addition, data stewards could then be given permissions to create artefacts and data products, define relevant data quality KPIs, and define the entities with which the data should be shared, giving them more autonomy in the process.

Achilleas Marinakis and Christos-Antonios Gizelis from [OTE](#), DATAMITE's partner leading the 'Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange' pilot. From a business perspective, OTE shows how the DATAMITE Framework can create new opportunities for data-driven innovation and improve operational efficiency in the energy sector.

Federico Piñuela García from [Grupo Gimeno](#), DATAMITE's partner leading the 'Corporate Multi-Domain Data Exchange with DIH Support' pilot. From a business perspective, Grupo Gimeno uses the advanced data-sharing and analytics capabilities of the DATAMITE framework to optimise processes and unlock new business.

Why is it important to have a legal partner in a data project?

POLINA PETROVA & DANIELA ILIEVA

LAW AND INTERNET FOUNDATION

At DATAMITE, our goal is to encompass every facet of data exchange and monetisation. To this end, **our consortium includes partners that extend beyond the technological and monetary fields**, such as the [Law and Internet Foundation](#) (LIF). LIF is responsible for providing thorough insights into the EU legal framework for data transfers, with a particular focus on the Regulation on the Free Flow of Non-Personal Data in the European Union and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

To illustrate the importance of having a legal partner on a project like DATAMITE, we interviewed Polina Petrova and Daniela Ilieva from LIF. They explained how their work enables the formulation of **tailored legal and ethical requirements** specific to the technical components of DATAMITE, ensuring their compliance with relevant legal and ethical requirements.

EVENTS

DATAMITE Plenary Meeting in Bilbao

From 8 to 10 April, the DATAMITE consortium held its first plenary meeting of 2025 in Bilbao, Spain. This important meeting was held to discuss the steps needed to achieve the project's goal before DATAMITE ends, presumably by the end of the year. As at the previous [plenary meeting in Aachen](#), the **agenda included a CodeCamp day** with the project's developers on the first day, **followed by two days with the entire consortium**. Each work package presented its progress and future steps.

In addition to three days of intensive work, the **DATAMITE consortium enjoyed a visit to the Guggenheim Museum**, followed by a traditional Basque dinner in the centre of Bilbao. Many thanks to our colleagues at [Tecnalia](#) for hosting the plenary meeting.

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DATAMITE's presence at Data Week 2025

[Data Week 2025](#), the spring gathering of Europe's Big Data and Data-Driven AI research and innovation community, took place in Athens, Greece, from 27 to 28 May. With the theme 'Odyssey of AI: Navigating the Data Seas', this year's edition focused on the **fundamental elements of data value creation**. As usual, **DATAMITE was well represented at the event**, with a presence in one workshop and as part of the EUDATA+ cluster.

On Tuesday 27, Christos Gizelis from [OTE](#) represented **DATAMITE** at the 'Monetisation & Governance Across Mobility, Media and Trustworthy Data Sharing' session. And, on 28 May, the last day of the conference, the [EUDATA+ cluster](#) held a **session** in the plenary room titled 'EUDATA+: Solutions for Data Trading and Marketplaces (Insight for the Future of AI and Data Spaces)'.

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DATAMITE at EGI 2025

The [EGI 2025 Conference](#) organised by [EGI Foundation](#) was held in Santander, Spain, from 2 to 6 June. The conference **brought together international scientific communities**, IT and service providers, European projects, security experts, community managers, and policy makers to discuss data research and innovation. **DATAMITE contributed to the conference** by exhibiting a poster showcasing some of the work done during the project and delivering a presentation, as well as displaying a project presentation video

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DATAMITE at SMARTCOMP 2025

The 2025 IEEE International Conference on Smart Computing ([SMARTCOMP](#)) took place from 16 to 19 June in Cork, Ireland. SMARTCOMP is **the leading conference in the field of smart computing**, which is a multidisciplinary domain based on advances in sensor-based technologies, the Internet of Things, cyber-physical systems, edge computing, big data analytics, machine learning, cognitive computing and artificial intelligence.

This year's conference programme included the 1st International Workshop on Smart AI Models and Data Sharing and Monetisation ([SmartAIDa](#)). SmartAIDa aimed to address the growing need for effective frameworks and technologies that enable the sharing, monetisation, and governance of AI models and datasets. **Jordi Arjona ([ITI](#)), DATAMITE's technical coordinator, was the keynote speaker**, and several consortium members presented DATAMITE-related papers.

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DATAMITE presents a paper poster at CIRED 2025

The [2025 CIRED - Conference and Exhibition on Electricity Distribution](#) took place from 16 to 19 June in Geneva, Switzerland. With over 1,600 people attending the conference and 3,000 people visiting the exhibition, CIRED is one of the **world's leading energy conferences**.

Ricardo Henriques from [E-REDES](#) travelled to Geneva to present a **paper poster on DATAMITE** at the exhibition. The paper, titled 'Sharing Electricity Distribution Data Through Energy Data Spaces Using the DATAMITE Framework', explores how Distribution System Operators (DSOs) **can share**

electricity distribution data via Energy Data Spaces using the DATAMITE Framework.

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